

Synthesis of *N*-Acetylsulphonylhydrazine Hydrochlorides

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Basic anilides have been synthesised in a large number and among these diethyl-amino-2, 6-dimethylacetanilide, xylocaine, is the best known local anaesthetic¹. Hibicon, a product having 4+ rating in both audiogenic and electroshock test, is found to be effective in the treatment of grand mal². Several monochloroacetyl derivatives of *p*-nitrophenyl alkyl amines have been found effective against *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*³. Basic *N*-benzylacetamides as potential local anaesthetics have been synthesised by Dalal and Trivedi⁴.

4-Aminobenzenesulphonylhydrazine, structurally related to sulphanilamide, was found to display an *in vitro* inhibition to the growth of *Escherichia coli* and *Streptococcus pyrogenes*. It is comparable with the activity of sulphadiazine. This compound proved, however, to be quite toxic in animal studies⁵.

It has been therefore thought of interest to proceed a step further in the modification of the amide structure in which sulphonamido group (-SO₂NH₂) and xylocaine group (-NHCOCH₂NR₂) are combined to give rise to compounds of the type R.SO₂NHNHCOCH₂NR₂. With this object in view, *N*-diethylamino-, morpholinyl-, and piperidinyl-acetylsulphonylhydrazines have been prepared by allowing chloroacetyl chloride to react with various sulphonylhydrazines and by subsequent treatment of the *N*-chloroacetyl-sulphonylhydrazines formed with secondary amines to yield the required *N*-(sub.)acetyl-sulphonylhydrazines.

The compounds prepared are described in Tables I to IV. One typical procedure in each case and variations, if any, are described, wherever applicable. (All melting points are uncorrected).

TABLE I
N-Chloroacetyl-phenyl/thienyl-sulphonylhydrazines.
R.SO₂NHNHCOCH₂Cl

R.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
C ₆ H ₅	163°	C ₈ H ₉ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	12.7	12.9	11.0	11.3
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	162°	C ₉ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ ClS	12.1	12.2	10.5	10.7
<i>p</i> -CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄	167°	C ₉ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂ ClS	11.2	11.5	9.9	10.1
<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	222°	C ₈ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S	11.0	11.3	9.5	9.9
<i>p</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	198°	C ₈ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂ BrClS	9.8	9.8	8.5	8.6
2-Thienyl	158°	C ₈ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂ ClS ₂	25.0	25.2	10.7	11.0
2-(5-Chloro)thienyl	157°	C ₈ H ₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S ₂	22.0	22.2	9.8	9.7
2-(5-Bromo)thienyl	159°	C ₈ H ₆ O ₂ N ₂ BrClS ₂	19.0	19.2	8.2	8.4
2-(5-Nitro)thienyl	167°(d)	C ₈ H ₆ O ₂ N ₃ ClS ₂	21.2	21.4	13.8	14.0

1. Logren and Lundquist, U.S. P. 2,441,498/1948; *Chem. Abst.*, 1948, 42, 6378.

2. Kushner et al., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, 16, 1283.

3. Imhiki and Kuwada, *J. Pharm. Soc., Japan*, 1952, 72, 69.

4. *This Journal*, 1960, 37, 437.

5. Zimmer et al., *J. Org. Chem.* 1959, 24, 1667.

TABLE II

N-Diethylaminoacetyl-phenyl/thienyl-sulphonylhydrazine hydrochlorides.
 $R.SO_2NHNHCOCH_2.N(C_2H_5)_2.HCl$

R.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
C_6H_5	175°	$C_{12}H_{20}O_3N_3ClS$	9.8	10.0	12.8	13.1
<i>p</i> - $CH_3C_6H_4$	152°(d)	$C_{13}H_{22}O_3N_3ClS$	9.5	9.5	12.3	12.5
<i>p</i> - $CH_3OC_6H_4$	172°	$C_{13}H_{20}O_4N_3ClS$	8.9	9.1	11.7	12.0
<i>p</i> - ClC_6H_4	180-82°(d)	$C_{12}H_{19}O_3N_3Cl_2S$	8.9	9.0	11.6	11.6
<i>p</i> - BrC_6H_4	180°	$C_{12}H_{19}O_3N_3BrClS$	7.9	8.0	10.1	10.5
2-Thienyl	107-109°	$C_{10}H_{18}O_3N_3ClS_2$	19.1	19.5	12.5	12.8

TABLE III

N-Morpholinylacetyl-phenyl/thienyl-sulphonylhydrazine hydrochlorides.

R.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
C_6H_5	149°	$C_{12}H_{18}O_4N_3ClS$	9.3	9.5	12.2	12.5
<i>p</i> - $CH_3C_6H_4$	154°(d)	$C_{13}H_{20}O_4N_3ClS$	9.0	9.2	11.7	12.0
<i>p</i> - $CH_3OC_6H_4$	158°	$C_{13}H_{20}O_5N_3ClS$	8.5	8.8	11.2	11.5
<i>p</i> - ClC_6H_4	163°	$C_{12}H_{17}O_4N_3Cl_2S$	8.6	8.7	11.1	11.4
<i>p</i> - BrC_6H_4	152°	$C_{12}H_{17}O_4N_3BrClS$	7.7	7.7	9.9	10.1
2-Thienyl	151°(d)	$C_{10}H_{16}O_4N_3ClS_2$	18.6	18.7	12.0	12.2
2-(5-Bromo)thienyl	135-37°	$C_{10}H_{15}O_4N_3BrClS_2$	15.0	15.2	9.9	10.0

TABLE IV

N-Piperidinylacetyl-phenyl/thienyl-sulphonylhydrazine hydrochlorides.

R.	M.P.	Formula.	% Sulphur.		% Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Reqd.	Found.	Reqd.
C_6H_5	185°	$C_{13}H_{20}O_3N_3ClS$	9.5	9.6	12.4	12.6
<i>p</i> - $CH_3C_6H_4$	185°(d)	$C_{14}H_{22}O_3N_3ClS$	9.0	9.2	11.9	12.1
<i>p</i> - $CH_3OC_6H_4$	201°	$C_{14}H_{22}O_4N_3ClS$	8.7	8.8	11.5	11.6
<i>p</i> - ClC_6H_4	177°	$C_{13}H_{19}O_3N_3Cl_2S$	8.6	8.7	11.1	11.4
<i>p</i> - BrC_6H_4	175°	$C_{13}H_{19}O_3N_3BrClS$	7.6	7.8	10.0	10.2
2-Thienyl	169°	$C_{11}H_{18}O_3N_3ClS_2$	18.6	18.9	12.1	12.4
2-(5-Bromo)thienyl	134-35°	$C_{11}H_{17}O_3N_3BrClS_2$	15.0	15.3	9.7	10.0

N.B. (d) denotes decomposition.

N-Chloroacetylbenzenesulphonylhydrazine.—To a suspension of benzenesulphonylhydrazine (1.72 g., 0.01 M) in water (10 ml), cooled in an ice-salt mixture, were added dropwise with vigorous shaking chloroacetyl chloride (1.25 g., 0.011 M) and 10% aqueous

NaOH solution (5 ml) simultaneously. After allowing the mixture to attain the room temperature, the precipitates were filtered, washed successively with cold water, HCl (1:1), and water. It was air-dried and crystallised from dilute ethanol; yield 1.44 g (58%), m.p. 163°. (Found: N, 11.0; S, 12.7. $C_8H_9O_3N_2ClS$ requires N, 11.3; S, 12.9%).

N-Diethylaminoacetyl-*p*-anisylsulphonylhydrazine Hydrochloride.—A mixture of *N*-chloroacetyl-*p*-anisylsulphonylhydrazine (2.8 g., 0.01 *M*) and diethylamine (1.46 g., 0.02 *M*) in absolute ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hours. The solvent was distilled. The residue was treated with a saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate and dissolved in HCl (dil.). The resultant solution was filtered, the filtrate treated with ammonia to liberate the base, and extracted with ether. The extract was dried with anhydrous $MgSO_4$, decanted, and dry HCl gas was passed into this solution. The hydrochloride obtained was crystallised from acetone in colorless platelets, m.p. 172°, yield 2.0 g. (58%). (Found: N, 11.7; S, 8.9. $C_{13}H_{22}O_4N_3ClS$ requires N, 12.0; S, 9.1%).

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